

Recommended citation: Servant-Miklos, V., & Guerra, A. (2019). Examining exemplarity in problem-based engineering education for sustainability. In Nagyn, B. V., Murphy, M., Järvinen, H.-M., & Kálmán, A. (Eds.), *Varietas delectat... Complexity is the new normality. SEFI 47th Annual Conference* (pp. 1022-1032). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Budapest, Hungary. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14656631.

Examining *Exemplarity* in Problem-Based Engineering Education for Sustainability

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Conference Key Areas: Strong demand for democratic involvement in educational processes, Sustainability reflecting the complexity of modern society.

Keywords: exemplarity, project-based learning, problem-based learning, sustainability

ABSTRACT

Oskar Negt's critical educational concept of exemplarity was a core component of problem-oriented, project based education in Denmark at its inception in the 1970s. Nearly fifty years on, this model of project education has grown in popularity around the world, especially in the field of engineering education. In the practice of engineering education today, while these projects have retained an interdisciplinary, practice-oriented, and experiential learning approach, the specific socio-historical aspects of exemplarity in Negt's theory have fallen by the wayside. In this paper, we ask whether these aspects have a place in twenty-first century engineering education, with a specific focus on the issue of sustainability, and what could be learned from exemplarity for curriculum design. The paper critically examines Negt's concept of exemplarity and its early application in project-based higher education in Denmark, then looks at the way in which it translated into engineering education, starting at Aalborg University, before appraising its relevance in the light of the growing number of sustainability issues covered in many engineering curricula.

1 INTRODUCTION

Problem-oriented, project-organized learning, often shortened to “PBL”, is an approach to engineering education pioneered in Denmark but now gaining popularity all over the world [1]. The essential characteristics of this approach are semester-long interdisciplinary group projects, complemented by disciplinary courses. Unlike the type of project work that is commonly found in secondary and vocational education, these projects are not designed as mere applications of protocols given by teachers, but as part of a problem-formulation process. One of the key requirements of problem-formulation is that it should be connected with real-life, or at least a realistic situation, rather than just abstract concepts.

The origins of this pedagogical approach is not to be found in engineering or technical education, but in the social sciences. Indeed, this model of education was developed in Germany and Denmark in the late 1970s as a response to traditional modes of higher education. It was implemented in several “radical” new universities with a strong left-wing brand of social sciences; most notably Bremen University and Roskilde University Centre [2]. The educational principles enunciated in these experiments were participant direction, problem-orientation, interdisciplinarity and exemplarity [3]. When the model was transferred to the newly opened Aalborg University in 1974, the managers were confronted with a challenge: unlike Bremen and Roskilde, Aalborg University (AAU) was dominated by a faculty of technical and natural sciences (TekNat), of which engineering was a big part. Suddenly, this pedagogical approach with a socialist analysis of the society had to be adapted to suit a study area mainly focused on technical and practical matters [4]. In practice, the engineering education programme retained the elements of participant-direction, loosely understood as student-centred learning within project groups, problem-orientation, in which the problems were practical problems, and interdisciplinarity, mostly within the technical field. The principle of exemplarity, as it was understood at Bremen and Roskilde, was not very much discussed at TekNat in the early years. There are several factors that account for this. Firstly, the principal author of the theory of exemplarity, Oskar Negt, was derided within some circles at AAU as an outdated Marxist, and those within the university (mainly social scientists) who followed him were criticised by sceptical colleagues [5]. Secondly, Negt wrote using 1970s Marxist jargon, and was therefore difficult to access for people without a background in philosophy or sociology, which the people running the engineering education programme did not have at that time [4]. Thirdly, the faculty of engineering at AAU was built on the merging of two pre-existing engineering education institutions in Aalborg, and many of the staff who were then transferred to Aalborg University were traditional teachers. Servant-Miklos and Spliid [4] have described how challenging the transition was for these teachers, in the light of which Negt’s exemplarity may simply have been a bridge too far. Finally, the pragmatic nature of engineering education itself makes problematic the development and application of educational concepts steeped in particular (e.g. dialectic materialist) ontological and epistemological paradigms, such as Negt’s exemplarity.

Nonetheless, the authors of this paper believe that there is a case to be made for a renewed understanding of the principle of exemplarity in engineering education today, adapted for the conditions and challenges of the 21st century, particularly the challenges brought about by climate change and the sustainability crisis. To begin, an explanation of what exemplarity is must be offered. Secondly, we must discuss whether exemplarity is still relevant in today’s context. Finally, we focus on the

concrete implications of exemplarity for engineering education, particularly when it comes to tackling issues of sustainability.

2 WHAT IS EXEMPLARITY?

There are historically two approaches to exemplarity, a purely pedagogical one, and a social-emancipatory one. The prime proponent of the former is Martin Wagenschein, and the latter Oskar Negt [6].

2.1. Pedagogical exemplarity: Wagenschein

For Wagenschein [7], exemplarity was a pedagogical method to reduce the contents overload in higher education curricula. By using good examples, through a process of analogy, students get an idea of the fundamental principles at stake (e.g. if I look at four or five different types of plants, I will have a good idea of how photosynthesis works). There is no requirement for this type of exemplarity to be either interdisciplinary or student-centred. In fact, teachers probably know better than the students which examples will be most conducive to understanding the principles required for the course learning objectives. Wagenschein expected that students would acquire learning habits that would make them more interested in their personal and cultural development. Therefore, from a disciplinary starting point, some form of interdisciplinary understanding would emerge.

2.2. Exemplarity as sociological imagination: Negt

Negt disagreed vehemently with Wagenschein [8]. Negt's starting point for exemplary learning was the sociological imagination. This is a concept developed by the American sociologist C. Wright Mills [9], to describe a situation where an individual is able to make sense of his or her personal circumstances in the light of global, historical, social, economic and political events. The sociological imagination is therefore what in technical terms would be called a *dialectic*. This means the opposition between two worldviews – the personal and the socio-historical – that reconcile into a viewpoint that understands the personal as social and the social as personal. To give a concrete example, the sociological imagination would provide farmers from the Mid-West of the USA who were subjected to historic flooding in early 2019 with the means to understand their personal losses within the broader context of human-induced climate change and its economic and social consequences, which would in turn spur them to take action, by protesting government inaction on climate change and voting out of office politicians who deny climate change, in the hope that this would in turn improve their circumstances. The sociological imagination has an explicit emancipatory element, meaning that it aims to empower people to take action for their personal and collective destinies within the socio-historical context. It is this emancipatory element that Negt latched onto in his conception of exemplarity. As a neo-Marxist, Negt's ambition was to free the working class from their oppressed condition through the power of exemplary education – that is, from the starting point of personal experience and practical examples issued from the everyday lives of workers, it must unveil the political economic conditions of society in its totality, and thereby provide a course to (political) action. It does this through the means of problem-orientation, participant direction, and interdisciplinarity, organized in the form of project work. Thus, exemplarity is a holistic project for Negt: it must be interdisciplinary to succeed, since social reality is not parceled into different

disciplines. Negt's exemplarity is harder to pinpoint in precise terms than Wagenschein's, which is probably why exemplarity has often been reduced to its purely pedagogical form.

2.3. The application of exemplarity in Danish higher education

The journey of exemplarity from Negt's writings about working class emancipation to higher educational practice goes through the Danish Student Union, where a group of committed socialist students led by Henning Salling Olesen endeavoured to translate exemplary learning into an actual educational programme [10]. The result was the problem-oriented, project work method of Roskilde University, though the contextual difference between the alienated workers of Negt and the middle-class Danish students at Roskilde was duly noted by critics [11]. Initially, this method did not involve any traditional courses at all: the students did their projects, and called in professors if they needed help with theory. An exception was already made from the beginning for natural sciences, where professors felt that students had to have some scientific basis before they could start work on their projects, and a division of 50/50 between project work and courses was admitted. After some battles with the government, the 50/50 division spread to the entire university, and was exported as such to Aalborg University, including at the faculty of engineering education.

When it comes to interdisciplinarity, the Roskilde programme offered a two-year interdisciplinary basic education programme in natural sciences, social sciences or humanities using the problem-oriented, project-based approach. In AAU, this was reduced to one year. In effect, interdisciplinarity has been waning over the years in all Danish problem-oriented, project-based education, especially with the Bologna European education reform and the pressures to fit a full bachelor in three years, instead of a more comprehensive programme over the course of five years. A recent reform at AAU has formalized the separation of the courses from the projects at Aalborg, thus entrenching the disciplinary approach even further. With regards to problem-orientation, it was explicitly social at Roskilde but became very practical in the faculty of engineering at Aalborg. Whereas Roskilde's Faculty of Social Sciences dealt in its early days with problems such as "imperialism, the Asian mode of production" and "Danish capitalism in crisis", the problems at the Technical Faculty of AAU were much more local and pragmatic, such as "sports hall at a school in Aalborg", or "swimming pool in a school in a village outside Aalborg" [2]. In theory, exemplarity can be reconciled with such a practical starting point – the starting point should, according to Negt, be in the practical experience of workers. But in practice, AAU was keen to avoid political connotations, especially by comparison with Roskilde [12], and the engineering educators discovered in the meantime some much more easily-accessible education theory, such as Piaget, Kolb and Dewey [4]. And thus, exemplarity in PBL for engineering education has since been loosely understood in a Wagenscheinian sense (as an example from which an analogy can be made).

3 IS EXEMPLARITY STILL RELEVANT TODAY?

There are aspects of Negt's theory that are not significantly relevant to engineering education today. In particular, the distinction between the bourgeoisie and proletariat is a 19th century distinction that is unhelpful to engineering educators, especially given the collapse of the blue collar working class around the developed world. Even in the case of developing countries, there are more useful ways to understand the social

dynamics at play in a globalized society than 19th century class dichotomies. As a result, the emphasis on class consciousness in Negt's exemplarity seems a bit unhelpful for contemporary educational challenges. However, we do believe that there is enough of relevance in Negt's theory, duly adapted to the conditions and problems of the 21st Century, to warrant promoting Negt's perspective on exemplarity as part of problem-based, project-organized engineering education, rather than using Wagenschein's restrictive conception of exemplarity.

Firstly, Negt is right to point out that examples treated merely as case-studies produce a fragmented, disciplinary view of reality, when true understanding comes from seeing the whole. In 2019, we live in a turbulent world that calls for broad, interdisciplinary analysis and action. The climate crisis, the staggering loss of biodiversity, the increase in ocean dead zones, the ongoing loss of massive swaths of rainforest, the plastic pollution crisis and other manifestations of the sustainability crisis cannot be treated as isolated problems, but must be seen as a part of the socio-economic system in which such a crisis was manufactured. Its impact on increasing inequalities, with the poorest on the planet being hit the hardest, must also be considered. Some of damage done by the crisis is already irreversible. We are on course to cross a threshold where it will be impossible to keep warming below 2 degrees Celsius in the coming two decades, according to the IPCC [13]. And yet, no technological "fixes" for the climate and sustainability crises are unproblematic. Take solar panels: where and how do we get the components to make them (and will this destabilize the places where we get them)? What do we do with them when they reach the end of their lifespans? How does building solar farms impact land use? How resilient are they to extreme weather events? What happens to people whose jobs and livelihoods depend on the fossil fuel industry? Another example is electric cars: where and how is the electricity produced? How are the batteries made and where are the components extracted? What happens to the enormous park of existing "dirty" vehicles? Is the effort to develop electric personal vehicles hampering the development of reliable, high speed public transportation? This doesn't even get into more difficult debates such as stratospheric aerosol injections and carbon capture and sequestration, which are nonetheless debates that our political paralysis on climate change will force us to have sooner rather than later. All students in all fields of study should be exposed to the systemic components of the crisis, but this is especially important for engineering students who will be working on many of the technological solutions.

Secondly, engineering students are also individuals embedded in a socio-historical fabric. Developing the sociological imagination should be a key responsibility of *all* higher education programmes in functioning democracies. In a technological world, this is especially important for engineering programmes. Our historical moment is one in which, as our dependence on technology reaches its zenith, the trust relationship between science and society has broken down and ordinary individuals increasingly believe and act on invalid propositions such as "climate change is a hoax" and "vaccines cause autism". Mills argued that for a democracy to function, a bridge had to be built between people's every day experiences and professional lives, and the political economy of the system. We would add that for a 21st century democracy to function, that bridge must also include a scientific and technological component, where technology is not just a thing you hold in your hand (a phone, a laptop) or a machine that will "solve" climate change, but is a network embedded in every level of our lives, from the mundane and personal to the professional and systemic. The sociological imagination today *is* technological and much as it is environmental. The historical

moment we are living through is made up of people who use technology, and people who design and produce it. Technology's impact and relationship with society and the biosphere can be revealed, analyzed and understood through exemplary learning. We will now look at what this means concretely.

4 EXEMPLARITY AND ENGINEERING EDUCATION FOR SUSTAINABILITY

Sustainability is without a doubt a key issue for engineering education in the 21st century. The establishment of communities of practice (for example annual conferences, research centers, journals), elective courses and programs on sustainability, tools to assess curriculum opportunities for sustainability (see for example STAUNCH® [14]), student organizations and sustainability councils, are all evidence that stakeholders in engineering education seek to engage with the sustainability crisis. The current aims are to provide students with experience, knowledge and competences to solve current sustainability problems and prevent future ones. Yet even though there are some good examples of sustainability integration in engineering education around the world, for instance through using the PBL approach, these efforts are still behind the needs. It is a fact that even as PBL is gaining popularity in engineering education around the world, the problems addressed and curriculum goals are, primarily, designed to train competences required by employers and accreditation systems [15], neither of which are currently aligned with the scale of the sustainability challenge before us.

Education for sustainability is still fragmented across disciplines, not considered a priority and added to the curriculum through elective and standalone courses, thereby lacking a systemic approach [16]. What we are not seeing much of are curricula that explicitly challenge disciplinary boundaries, including between humanities and the technical sciences, treat the issue with the urgency it deserves, and involves students, staff and management in the possibility of a paradigm shift [17]. Partly, this is because higher education institutions, disciplinary areas and teaching cultures are notoriously resistant to change. Within engineering faculties, prejudices and misconceptions about sustainability abound, combined with bloated curricula that cannot accommodate any more contents, but which seem impossible to condense. Poor staff training, leading to a lack of practical knowledge on curriculum development is also a barrier, which contributes to slow institutional change and integration of sustainability [16].

4.1. Exemplary problems for a systemic understanding

While it's true that both Wagenschein and Negt's perspectives on exemplarity can contribute to the integration of sustainability in engineering education by helping to overcome some of the barriers previously stated, we believe that only Negt's perspective permits the possibility of a paradigm shift in the institutions and students' way of thinking about sustainability. Negt's concept of exemplarity goes beyond the purely pedagogical. Furthermore, there is a clear link here between the work of Sterling on sustainable education [18] and Negt, as Sterling calls for sustainable education to be transformative, interdisciplinary, contextual, action-and problem-oriented. As we have seen, sustainability is a complex and interdisciplinary problem by definition. Consequently, the type of problems that students confront in their projects, and the learning process they go through should reflect that complexity. In that sense, merely replacing existing disciplinary knowledge with "sustainability knowledge", or adding it, in the engineering curriculum, it perpetuates the so-called

“technocratic approach”. What is needed instead is a holistic and systems thinking approach when integrating sustainability in engineering, that does not compromise on technical excellence but embeds in within a relevant socio-historical context. The curriculum must be organized around “exemplary problems” with the following characteristics: grounded in the experience of students and “real life”, requiring to involve different stakeholders, to be addressed from a multiplicity of angles, calls on high level technical knowledge and competences, able to provide an analysis that goes from the specific to the systemic, that takes into account the contingent, historical, social, economic and political context of technology. For example, taking a starting point as concrete as a project-problem that examines the planning of a cycle paths network, or the development of a new plastic recycling process can absolutely be exemplary in the Negtian sense, provided that students are guided in the problem-formulation process to consider the dialectic between the specific technical situation described by the problem and the systemic issues it raises. But students do seem to struggle to look at specific sustainability problems as systemic issues. For example, our experience in talking to students who study plastic recycling is that they have developed a keen interest in sorting their own waste and recycling in general, from an individual perspective, which is a good step, but hardly any of them question the scale of the production and consumption of plastic or the “throwaway” culture in which these are embedded, which is what the sociological imagination would require. Fixating on individual action and fragmented problems is precisely one of the issues that Negt raised against Wagenschein’s exemplarity.

4.2 Building up problems from narrow to open and complex

It is fair to say, though, that throwing students at the deep end in their first year may be a big ask. It is possible to gradually build up to truly exemplary problem, though. As a model to progressively include the sociological imagination in the practice of PBL, we can look to Savin-Baden’s five PBL models [19], which provide a holistic view of PBL environments and propose dimensions through which to organize learning around problems. The models move from narrow and well-defined with focus on the development of disciplinary knowledge (model I and II), to more ill-defined and complex problems with focus on metacognition and interdisciplinary knowledge (models III, IV, V) (*Fig. 1.*). Thus, on the one hand, a limited case scenario with sustainability components, written by content experts and tutored for a small group of students by teachers within a specific disciplinary field could fit within models I or II, and make use of Wagenscheinian exemplarity. This approach to PBL is popular in vocational technical education, for instance at polytechnic institutions. On the other hand, an open problem, defined across disciplines by students under the guidance of teachers from an array of specialties could correspond to model V, and is suited to using Negt’s approach to exemplarity.

Model	Knowledge	Learning goals	Problem scenario	Students	Facilitator	Assessment	State of sustainability education
(I) PBL for epistemological competence	<i>Knowing-what</i>	Use and management of knowledge	Limited-solutions already known	Receivers and problem solvers	A guide to correct propositional knowledge	Test of epistemological competence	Education about sustainability ↓ Education for sustainability ↓ Education as sustainability
(II) PBL for professional action	<i>Know-how</i>	Outcome focused acquisition	Real life situations	Pragmatics induced by professional culture	Demonstrator of skills	Testing competencies for work place	
(III) PBL for interdisciplinary understanding	<i>Know-what & know how</i>	Synthesis of knowledge across disciplines	Knowledge to act and interact	Integrator of boundaries	Coordinator of knowledge and skills	Skills and contextual knowledge	
(IV) PBL for trans-disciplinary learning	<i>Reconstruction</i>	Critical thought from subject positions	Resolving and managing dilemmas	Independent thinkers	Orchestrator of opportunities	Demonstrate an integrated understanding	
(V) PBL for critical contestability	<i>Contingent, contextual & constructed</i>	A hybrid imagination	Multidimensional and open	Explorers' of underlying assumptions	Commentator, a challenger and decoder	Open-ended and flexible	

Fig. 1. Savin-Baden PBL models as framework for Education for Sustainability (according to [16]).

In this *PBL for critical contestability*, the knowledge is characterised as contingent (i.e. depends on or is conditioned by other factors), contextual and constructed by the learner for given situations. The problem scenario is open, multidimensional and ill-structured. In the literature on education for sustainability, these problems are referred as “wicked problems” and call for multidisciplinary collaboration, innovation and critical thinking [20]. In this context, a problem scenario is a point of departure for problem identification, analysis and formulation and not a mere case provided by academic staff (exemplarity in the Wagenscheinian sense). Furthermore, the variety of PBL models also provides engineering educators with a framework for progressively developing engineering curricula for towards a transformative study of sustainability, starting with narrow problems with younger and less experienced students, focus on disciplinary knowledge and competences (including sustainability as a discipline), and increasing the complexity and openness of the problems and the interdisciplinarity of the projects as the students gain experience.

4.3. Educating the educators

Even when they are working on open problems, students shouldn't be left entirely to their own devices. At Aalborg University for instance, in some engineering education programmes, the project-problems are guided by a semester theme, defined by the teachers [21]. Developing real, complex, ill-structured themes wherein “wicked” problem scenarios can be identified and interdisciplinary sustainability issues are central, calls on teachers to collaborate and share their knowledge across disciplinary areas whilst empowering students to take action. Teachers need to be trained not only to work together in such a way but also on sustainability and how to integrate it on their own teaching/ discipline. Working beyond disciplines is a skill that needs to be

developed, especially when teachers have been themselves educated and working for years within disciplinary boundaries. For this to happen, resources needed to be allocated in order to develop staff training and development courses on education for sustainability, reward systems and curriculum flexibility to set-up, for example, sustainability projects across departments and faculties [16].

4.3. Addressing curriculum overload

The overload of the curriculum is a problem in contemporary engineering education, as in many other higher educational studies, and is often used as an “excuse” to exclude sustainability issues. And yet this is happening in an age where knowledge is constantly produced and changing the way humans understand and interact with both technology and the biosphere, shortening the half-life of facts learned in the classroom. Simply adding more facts to the curriculum, even facts about the sustainability crisis, will only make the issue worse if students are not given the means to process the overload of information. Wagenschein understood the power of examples and analogy in reducing cognitive overload for students, but what he did not see was that those examples could function as more than mere analogies, and rather as entry points into systemic issues that could function as an organizing principle for knowledge. Modern curriculum designers must not be afraid to cut out large amounts of contents, and trust in students to acquire specific contents as and when they need it in their professional careers. Instead, engineering students at university must learn to understand the system in which technology operates, examine it from all angles, thereby providing what in constructivist language we would call a “cognitive schema” in which future knowledge can be processed by the mind. In essence, this picks up on the distinction between know-what, how (education about sustainability), know-why, when and where (education for/ as sustainability) [16].

5 CONCLUSION

In sum, using exemplary learning could support the integration of sustainability education in engineering studies. First, through an alignment of sustainability learning principles with Negt’s concept and type of problems used. Second, by organizing the curriculum around exemplary problem, where both technical expertise and a systemic understanding of sustainability can be developed dialectically to educate technically excellent engineers that have a holistic understanding of the sustainability crisis. There are, around the world, several examples of problem-oriented, project-organized cases where exemplary learning is explicit [16, p.81], see for example, the elective programme from Arizona State University (US), GlobalResolve [21].

The central issue with developing exemplarity on a larger scale in engineering education programmes is that engineering education is currently a reflection of ministerial mandates for specific contents and competences that are largely driven by a market logic and only have a technocratic view of sustainability. These mandates are then pushed through via accreditation boards who would not look favourably on paradigm shifting approaches. However, the rise in new environmental movements around the world and the speed at which climate change and other environmental issues are taking a toll on the planet currently is starting to shift the discourse, and may mean that exemplarity’s time has come for engineering educators.

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